

EXPEDITION REPORT

Expedition dates: 07 – 22 January 2023

Report published: January 2025

**Ways of the desert:
Conserving Arabian oryx, Gordon's
wildcat and other species of the Dubai
Desert Conservation Reserve,
United Arab Emirates.**

محمية دبي الصحراوية
DUBAI DESERT CONSERVATION RESERVE

EXPEDITION REPORT

Ways of the desert: Conserving Arabian oryx, Arabian wildcat and other species of the Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve, United Arab Emirates.

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Abstract

The successful collaboration between Biosphere Expeditions and the Dubai Desert Conservation Reserve (DDCR), initiated in 2012, continues with citizen scientists collecting data for the tenth successive expedition from 07 to 22 January 2023.

The 2023 expedition's quadrant surveys recorded the following species from 256 random observations and 62 circular observations: 512 Arabian oryx *Oryx leucoryx*, 299 Arabian gazelle *Gazella arabica*, 267 sand gazelle *Gazella marica*, 28 Arabian great shrikes *Lanius excubitor aucheri*, 13 lappet-faced vultures *Torgos tracheliotos*, 1 MacQueen's bustards *Chlamydotis macqueenii*, 2 Arabian hares *Lepus capensis*, 9 greater hoopoe larks *Alaemon alaudipes* and 10 pharaoh eagle-owl *Bubo ascalaphus*.

As the population size of ungulates in the fenced DDCR is pretty much known, the expedition concentrated its research work on elucidating animal distribution. Arabian oryx were distributed more in the south of DDCR, mainly around feed points and vegetated dunes. Arabian gazelles were concentrated in the central and central-south parts of the DDCR, mainly in gravel plains, around irrigated areas and under ghaf trees. Sand gazelles were mainly observed in sand dunes, as well as around the irrigated areas, where there is more forage to be found.

The expedition's Arabian red fox survey found 118 dens, of which 26 had previously been classified as active or inactive during the 2020 expedition, with an additional 32 newly identified dens. The 2023 surveys showed an increase in the number of surveyed or identified active and inactive dens compared to 2020, despite the difficulty of this task for citizen scientists. Red foxes were also recorded on three camera traps during the 2023 expedition. Due to the favourable vegetation conditions after the rains, the red fox prey base is likely to have improved in the reserve. All these are positive indicators for the status of the fox population inside the DDCR, even though the den surveys might suggest otherwise.

Seven camera traps produced a total of 135 camera trapping days and captured 4,574 images, 2,066 with recognisable subjects, of which 1,700 were of native fauna, as well as 366 of humans or vehicles. Arabian oryx was the second most abundant and first most widespread species with 65 individuals recorded from 7 camera traps. Among the target mammal species within the DDCR, a possible Arabian wildcat was recorded for a third year in a row by camera trap. Arabian red fox was also recorded by three camera traps and rare species records include the Arabian hare and a lesser jerboa. Sand fox, lappet-faced vulture and pharaoh eagle-owl were not recorded by camera trap in 2023.

Over the years the relatively high numbers of ungulates within the DDCR, especially the Arabian oryx, continue to be a challenge in terms of the need to balance animal welfare with the health of the desert ecosystem. Supplying supplementary feed for the Arabian oryx herd had addressed both of these aspects by making additional food available to individuals while limiting the impact of overgrazing on the ecosystem. However, supplementary feeding also contributes to the continued growth of ungulate populations, which is not sustainable because both natural and supplied resources are limited. Therefore, in order to reduce the number of ungulates in the reserve, management has constructed ungulate holding enclosures outside the reserve perimeter. Translocation of surplus animals to other reserves within the natural home range of the species has been approved. A reduction in the ungulate population within the DDCR will hopefully lead to better vegetation and a distribution more dependent on habitat type and quality, rather than supplementary feed and enhanced (irrigated) habitats. Predator re-introduction has not been approved at this time by the authorities, but is still under consideration.

ملخص

يسد تمر التعاون ال ناجح بين بعثات بيوسفير اكسبيديشنز ومحمية دبي الصحراوية، الذي بدأ في عام ٢٠١٢ لبعثات شعاعا في فاشك تسالا فتبع بل تاناي بلا عمج ونطاوملاء لمعلا لصاوي ثيح، ال توالي من ٧ إلى ٢٢ ناير ٢٠٢٣ .

سجلت المسوحات الرباعية للبعثة الاسكتشافية لعام ٢٠٢٣ الأذواع ال تالية من ٢٥٦ ملاحظة عشوائية و ٦٢ ملاحظة دائرية : ٥١٢ من امها العربي (Oryx leucorys)، ٢٩٩ غزالاً عربياً (Gazella arabica)، ٢٦٧ عزالاً رملياً (Gazella marica)، ٢٨ من طائر الصرد العربي الكبير (Lanius excubitor)، ١٣ من نسر الأذن (Torgos tracheliotos)، ١ حبارى آسيوية (Chlamydotis macqueenii)، ٢ من الارانب البرية (Lepus capensis)، ٩ من طيور الهدهد الأكبر (Alaemon alaudipes)، و ١٠ من البوهة الصحراوية (Bubo ascalaphus).

ونظراً لأن حجم أعداد نوات الحوافر في المنطقة المسجلة من المحمية معروف إلى حد كبير، فقد ركزت البعثة عملها ال بدثي على توضح توزيع ال حيوانات. توزعت امها العربي بشكل أكبر في جنوب المحمية، ال غزلان وبشكل رئيسي حول نقاط ال تغذية والكتبان ال نباتية. وتركزت العرب في الأجزاء الوسطى والوسطى ال جنوبية من المحمية، وبشكل رئيسي في السهول الحصوية، حول المناطق المروية وتحت أشجار الغاف. أما ال غزلان الرملية فقد شوهدت بشكل رئيسي في ال كتبان الرملية، وكذلك حول المناطق المروية، حيث يوجد المزيد من العلف.

ح الذي أجرته ال بعثة الاسكتشافية للثعلب العربي الأحمر وجد المس ١١٨ وكراً، منها ٢٦ وكراً تم تصنيفها سابقاً على أنها نشطة أو غير نشطة خلال بعثة عام ٢٠٢٠، مع ٣٢ وكراً إضافياً تم تحديدها حديثاً. أظهرت مسوحات عام ٢٠٢٣ هاوت حديد دهامقارنة زيادة في عدد الأوكار ال نشطة وغير ال نشطة ال تي تم مسح بعام ٢٠٢٠، على الرغم من صعوبة هذه المهمة بالنسبة للعلماء المواطنين. كما سجلت أيضاً ثلاثة من الكاميرات الفخية الثعالب الحمراء خلال بعثة ٢٠٢٣. بسبب الظروف ال نباتية المواتية بعد هطول رقدت حسنت في المحمية. كل هذه مؤشرات الأمطار، من المرجح أن تكون قاعدة فرائس ال ثعلب الأحمر إيجابية لحالة تجمعات ال ثعالب داخل محمية، على الرغم من أن مسوحات الأوكار قدت وحي بخلاف ذلك.

انتجت سبعة من الكاميرات الفخية اجمالي ١٣٥ يوماً من التصوير والتقطت ٤٥٧٤ صورة، حيث ٢٠٦٦ صورة يمكن التعرف على محتواها، ومنها ١٧٠٠ صورة لحيوانات محلية، و ٣٦٦ صورة لأشخاص او مركبات. كان امها العربي ثاني أكثر الأنواع وفرة والأول من حيث الانتشار، حيث تم تسجيل ٦٥ فرداً من ٧ كاميرات فخية. من بين أنواع الثدييات المستهدفة داخل المحمية، كان هناك تسجيل محتمل للقط البري العربي للسنة الثالثة على التوالي بواسطة الكاميرا الفخية. كما تم تسجيل ثعلب أحمر عربي بواسطة ثلاثة من الكاميرات الفخية، ومن بين الأذواع ال نادرة الأرنب البري العربي والجرذ الأصغر. لم يتم تسجيل ثعلب الرمل والنسر ذو الوجه المرقط وبغاء النسر ال فرعون بواسطة مصيدة الكاميرا في عام ٢٠٢٣.

وعلى مر السنين، لا تزال الأعداد الكبيرة نسبياً من نوات الحوافر داخل محمية دبي الصحراوية، اهملا صاخو، العربي، تشكل تحدياً من حيث الحاجة إلى تحقيق التوازن بين رفاهية الحيوانات وصحة النظام البيئي الصحراوي. وقد عالجت وفير العلف ال تكميلي لقطع امها العربي كلاهين ال جاندين من خلال توفير غذاء إضافي للأفراد مع الحد من التأثير الرعي الجائر على النظام البيئي. ومع ذلك، تساهم التغذية التكميلية أيضاً في استمرار نمو أعداد نوات الحوافر، لبطبيعة والموارد وهو أمر غير مستدام لأن الموارد المتوفرة محدودة. ولذلك، ومن أجل تقليل عدد نوات الحوافر في المحمية، قامت الإدارة ببناء حظائر لحدس نوات الحوافر خارج محيط المحمية. وقد تمت الموافقة على نقل ال حيوانات ال فاضلة إلى محميات أخرى داخل النطاق ال يعي لهذه الأذواع. يندخ فاضل أعداد نوات الحوافر ومن الأمول أن يندخ داخل المحمية إلى تحسب ال غطاء ال نباتي وال توزيع الذي يمتد بشكل أكبر على نوع الموائل وجودتها، بدلاً من الأعلاف التكميلية والموائل المحسنة (المروية). لم تتم الموافقة على إعادة توطين الحيوانات المقترس طات، ولا كنها لا تزال قيد الدراسة في الوقت الحالي من قبل ال سل.

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1. Expedition review

M. Hammer
Biosphere Expeditions

1.1. Background

Background information, location, conditions and the general research area are as described in [Sher Shan et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2019\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2018\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2016\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2015\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2014\)](#), [Bell et al. \(2013\)](#).’

1.2. Dates & team

The 2023 expedition comprised of two one-week groups from 7 to 23 January 2023 with a team of international citizen and professional scientists, as well as an expedition leader. The expedition team was recruited by Biosphere Expeditions and consisted of a mixture of ages, nationalities, and backgrounds. They were (in alphabetical order and with country of residence):

7 – 14 January 2023: Zdenek Benes (Switzerland), Anneke Berendts (Netherlands), Mandy Geithner (Germany), Peter Goodman (UK), Mark Keegan (USA), Petra Klavehn (Germany), Jenny Lantair (UK), Simone Mattstedt (Germany), Elisa Munoz Franco (Switzerland), Emilie Rebert (UAE), Sammy Six (UAE), Patricia Smith (Belgium).

Figure 1.2a. Expedition team 1.

16 – 23 January 2023: Jim Blomgren (USA), Lilly, Norma & Robert Elkind (USA), Peter Goodman (UK), Gary Jones (China), Rupa Kapitzki (UAE), Owais Khand (UK), Monika Sax (Germany), Betsy & Peter Snow (USA), Andreas Zemann (Germany).

Figure 1.2b. Expedition team 2.

The DDCR team for the expedition consisted of Conservation Officers Aline Witte and Basil Roy, as well as Conservation Manager Gerhard Erasmus. Support personnel included Dr Matthias Hammer from Biosphere Expeditions. A medical umbrella, safety and evacuation procedures were in place, but did not have to be invoked as there were no incidences.

The expedition scientist was Aline Witte de la Torre, with a BSc in Biology from the *Universidad Autonoma de Nuevo Leon*. Her conservation career started at ARCAS Wildlife Rescue and Rehabilitation Centre in Guatemala, working in the rehabilitation and release of birds, mammals, and reptiles. Upon returning to Mexico, she worked at Chipinque Ecological Park implementing conservation projects, managing GIS data, and monitoring key species to assess ecosystem health. Aline joined the DDCR in September 2022. Her current role is to provide support for the completion of the DDCR Visitors Centre, manage and update GIS data, conduct new research, and implement long-term wildlife monitoring programs. She was supported by the DDCR Management team.

The expedition was led by Malika Fettak, who is half Algerian, but was born and educated in Germany. She majored in Marketing & Communications and is a qualified systemic NLP Master Coach and Family Constellation leader. She joined Biosphere Expeditions in 2008, ran the German-speaking operations and the German office for some years, and has led expeditions all over the world. She is passionate about nature, the outdoors, foreign cultures, people, and team building. She has travelled extensively, is multilingual, a qualified off-road driver, diver, and outdoor first aider.

1.3. Partners

The main partner on this expedition is the Dubai Conservation Board, a government-appointed organisation concerned with the conservation and protection of the Dubai inland desert. Other partners include the National Avian Research Centre.

1.4. Acknowledgements

This study was conducted by Biosphere Expeditions, which runs wildlife conservation expeditions all over the globe. Without our expedition team members (listed above) who provided an expedition contribution and gave up their spare time to work as research assistants, none of this research would have been possible. The support team and staff (also mentioned above) were central to making it all work on the ground. Biosphere Expeditions would also like to thank the DDCR and its staff, and the Friends of Biosphere Expeditions for their sponsorship and/or in-kind support. Thank you also to anonymous reviewers for helpful comments on drafts of this report.

1.5. Further information & enquiries

More background information on Biosphere Expeditions in general and on this expedition in particular including pictures, diary excerpts, and a copy of this report can be found on the Biosphere Expeditions website www.biosphere-expeditions.org.

A multimedia expedition diary is available on <https://blog.biosphere-expeditions.org/category/expedition-blogs/arabia-2023/>.

Expedition reports of this and all other expeditions are available on <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Biosphere-Expeditions-Matthias-Hammer>

Figure 1.5a. Desert landscape in the study site.

1.6. Expedition budget

Each team member paid towards expedition costs a contribution of € 1,770 per person for the 8-day group. The contribution covered accommodation and meals, supervision and induction, special research equipment and all transport from and to the team assembly point. It did not cover excess luggage charges, travel insurance, personal expenses such as telephone bills, souvenirs etc., or visa and other travel expenses to and from the assembly point (e.g. international flights). Details on how this contribution was spent are given below.

Income	€
Expedition contributions	41,017
Expenditure	
Staff includes local and Biosphere Expeditions staff salaries and travel expenses	6,973
Research includes research materials & gear etc. purchased internationally & locally	2,815
Transport includes hire cars, fuel, taxis in the UAE	3,870
Expedition base includes all food & services	4,612
Administration includes miscellaneous fees & sundries	2,188
Team recruitment Arabia as estimated % of annual PR costs for Biosphere Expeditions	7,334
Income – Expenditure	13,225
Total percentage spent directly on project	68%

2. Desert species surveys

2.1. Introduction and background

Previous work from 2012 to 2020 (there were no expeditions in 2021 and 2022 due to the COVID pandemic) and background to the study site and species under investigation are as per [Sher Shan et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2020\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2019\)](#), [Simkins & Hammer \(2018\)](#), [Simkins et al. \(2016\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2015\)](#), [Bell & Hammer \(2014\)](#), [Bell et al. \(2013\)](#).

2.2. Survey aims

- Species encounter surveys in quadrats to understand the distribution of the three ungulate species and other target species in DDCR.
- Arabian red fox *Vulpes vulpes arabica* den surveys to monitor population changes of the DDCR's largest predator species through their den use.
- Camera trapping to record nocturnal and cryptic species.
- Pharaoh eagle-owl *Bubo ascalaphus* survey to evaluate population status and nesting behaviour.
- Lappet-faced vulture *Torgos tracheliotos* survey to study movements and population status of visiting vultures.

2.3. Survey design and training of citizen scientists

Citizen scientists received species and methodology training at the beginning of each expedition group. Presentations about identification of ungulate and other target species were also part of the training sessions.

Surveys were conducted in four zones, namely north, central, south, and perimeter (Figure 2.3a). Each zone comprised fifteen 2 x 2 km quadrants, with only the perimeter zone having 17 partial quadrants. These 62 quadrants together represent approximately 214 km², or 95%, of the 225 km² of the DDCR and included all key habitats of vegetated dunes, sand dunes, and gravel plains. Citizen scientists were tasked to record any animal species observed in the field while not performing surveys as random observations. Four Garmin Montana GPS units (models 600 & 680) were loaded with all the relevant geo-referenced data needed for surveys (Figure 2.3a), such as reserve polygon, main roads, 2 x 2 km grid, survey points, and areas, office, and camp locations. Teams of three to four citizen scientists were formed daily, allowing citizen scientists to participate in different surveys during the expedition. The GPS units were distributed among citizen scientists, one per team, to perform the surveys.

2.3.1. Species encounter surveys in quadrants

This survey recorded species encountered through circular observations and random encounters. During circular observations, each team of three or four citizen scientists selected an observation point within 300 m of the centre of the quadrant marked on their GPS. Each observation point had a good view so that the citizen scientists were able to record all species (and their individuals) seen by eye or through binoculars within 30 minutes and 360°. This provided a snapshot of animal distribution and numbers in the quadrant. The survey was conducted between 07:00 and 17:00 over two weeks, covering all 62 quadrants (214 km²). Random encounters were those made during the expedition when not conducting circular observations, whilst driving to set a camera trap or on supply runs. Data gathered included species name, GPS position of researcher when the species was first seen, time of day when the species was observed, and ecological information such as the number of animals (group size), sex, age, behaviour, and any additional comments. IDW (Inverse Distance Weighted Interpolation) was used to analyse data (Moayyed Sher Shah, 2020).

2.3.2. Arabian red fox den surveys

All previously identified dens from the 2020 expedition were revisited, along with dens found during a 2022 study done by the American University of Central Asia (AUCA). All revisited dens were reclassified based on signs of fox activity such as tracks, fresh digging, prey remains, and fresh scat (Moayyed Sher Shah, 2020). Dens were classified as abandoned if the den had filled in with sand or could not be found. In addition, any new dens found were recorded, classified and georeferenced. The density estimations of red fox dens in the DDCR were then calculated using ArcGIS software tools based on Kernel density estimates (Moayyed Sher Shah, 2020).

2.3.3. Camera trapping

Nine camera traps (one Reconyx HF2X and eight Bushnell Trophy Cam HD) were distributed across the DDCR's north, central, south, and perimeter zones. Predetermined locations in each of the zones were chosen for survey groups to set their camera traps, all of which were on natural sites (sand dunes and gravel plains away from man-made waterholes). All camera traps were set to capture three pictures with trigger at a 10 second interval. Camera traps were not baited and were left out in the field for fifteen days. SD cards were swapped at the end of each group's stay so participants would have a chance to see what each team's camera captured.

2.3.4. Pharaoh eagle-owl survey

Citizen scientists visited pre-selected survey sites in the north, central, and south zones, as well as nesting and roosting sites previously identified by DDCR staff during the 2022 breeding season. They surveyed a total of 23 sites to check for pharaoh eagle-owl presence, signs of activity (such as pellets), and nests. Data gathered included sighting time and coordinates, number of individuals seen, behaviour (roosting, flying, etc.), nest presence and location, number of eggs, and any relevant comments. Sightings were also registered during circular observations and random observations.

2.3.5. Lappet-faced vulture survey

Citizen scientists visited four previously selected sites every day before 15:00 (Figure 2.3.5a) to record lappet-faced vulture individuals, as well as any other vulture species, present at each site. Three of the selected sites were located at waterholes where camera trap data showed high vulture activity. The fourth site was a dedicated carcass dumping site used by DDCR staff to study vulture feeding ecology. If no vultures were present at time of arrival, citizen scientists selected an inconspicuous viewpoint and monitored the site for up to 40 minutes. Data gathered included date, time, site coordinates, weather conditions, group size, number of adults and juveniles, behaviour, additional species, and their numbers.

Figure 2.3.5a. Lappet-faced vulture survey sites.

2.4. Results

Table 2.4a shows all species encountered during the 2023 expedition. Encounter methods included sightings and camera trapping as indicated. Invasive species were excluded.

Table 2.4a. Species encountered during the expedition with encounter type. Starred* species denotes expedition target species.

Common name	Scientific name	Sighting	Camera trap
Birds			
Grey francolin	<i>Francolinus pondicenus</i>	X	X
Egyptian goose	<i>Alopochen aegyptiaca</i>	X	
Little grebe	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	X	
Lappet-faced vulture	<i>Torgos tracheliotos*</i>	X	
Pallid harrier	<i>Circus macrourus</i>	X	
Long-legged buzzard	<i>Buteo rufinus*</i>	X	
MacQueen's bustard	<i>Chlamydotis macqueenii*</i>	X	
Common moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	X	
Red-wattled lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	X	
Pharaoh eagle-owl	<i>Bubo ascalaphus</i>	X	
Eurasian hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	X	
Green bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	X	
Arabian great shrike	<i>Lanius excubitor aucheri*</i>	X	
Arabian babbler	<i>Turdoides squamiceps</i>	X	X
Brown-necked raven	<i>Corvus ruficollis</i>	X	
Greater hoopoe-lark	<i>Alaemon alaudipes*</i>	X	
Crested lark	<i>Galerida cristata</i>	X	
Pale crag martin	<i>Ptyonoprogne obsoleta</i>	X	
Desert wheatear	<i>Oenanthe deserti</i>	X	X
Northern whetear	<i>Oenanthe oenanthe</i>	X	
Common swift	<i>Apus apus</i>	X	
White wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	X	
Purple sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	X	
Helmeted guineafowl	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	X	
Grey heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	X	
Black-crowned sparrow-lark	<i>Eremopterix nigriceps</i>	X	
Eurasian collared dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	X	X

Table 2.4a. (continued). Species encountered by the expedition with encounter type. Starred* species denotes expedition target species.

Common name	Scientific name	Sighting	Camera trap
Arthropods			
Tiger butterfly	<i>Danaus chrysippus</i>	X	
Emperor dragonfly	<i>Anax imperator</i>	X	
Long-horned grasshopper	<i>Truxalis fitzgeraldi</i>	X	
Hollow hopper	<i>Pyrgomorpha conica</i>	X	
Dune sand grasshopper	<i>Sphingotus rubescens</i>	X	
Sand wasp	<i>Bembix sp.</i>		X
Desert runner (ant)	<i>Cataglyphis niger</i>	X	X
Giant ant	<i>Camponotus xerxes</i>		X
Arabian darkling beetle	<i>Pimelia arabica</i>	X	
Mammals			
Arabian oryx	<i>Oryx leucoryx</i> *	X	X
Arabian gazelle	<i>Gazella arabica</i> *	X	X
Sand gazelle	<i>Gazella marica</i> *	X	X
Cat	<i>Felis sp.</i>		X
Arabian red fox	<i>Vulpes vulpes arabica</i> *	X	X
Arabian hare	<i>Lepus capensis</i>	X	X
Gerbil (tracks)	<i>Gerbillus sp.</i>	X	
Lesser Egyptian jerboa	<i>Jaculus jaculus</i>	X	X
Reptiles			
Arabian toad-headed agama	<i>Phrynocephalus arabicus</i>	X	
White spotted lizard	<i>Acanthodactylus schmidti</i>	X	
Fringe-toed sand lizard	<i>Acanthodactylus gongrorhynchatus</i>	X	
Schokari sand racer	<i>Psammophis schokari</i>	X	

2.4.1 Species encounter in quadrants

From 197 random observations and 62 circular observations, citizen scientists observed 512 Arabian oryx, 299 Arabian gazelles, 267 sand gazelles, 28 Arabian great grey shrikes, 13 lappet-faced vultures, one MacQueen's bustard, two Arabian hares, nine greater hoopoe-larks and five pharaoh eagle-owls.

Arabian oryx

Group 1 recorded 243 individuals while group 2 recorded 269, with a total of 512 Arabian oryx recorded during the expedition. Arabian Oryx showed a clear preference for the south of the reserve (Figure 2.4.1a).

Figure 2.4.1a. Arabian oryx distribution 2023.

Predicted distribution calculations are based on a combination of random and circular observations data.

Arabian gazelle

Group 1 recorded 146 Arabian gazelles while group 2 recorded 153, totalling 299 Arabian gazelles counted. The main concentration of Arabian gazelles was in the central and central-south parts of the DDCR, with a single point in the north; mainly in gravel plains, around the irrigated areas in old farms and resting under ghaf trees (Figure 2.4.1b).

Figure 2.4.1b. Arabian gazelle distribution 2023. Predicted distribution calculations are based on a combination of random and circular observations data.

Sand gazelle

Group 1 recorded 178 individuals, while group 2 recorded 89, yielding a total of 265 sand gazelles counted. Sand gazelles were mainly observed in sand dunes, as well as around the irrigated areas. As in previous expeditions, the largest concentration of sand gazelles was recorded at Ruwayyan farm in the DDCR's central north of DDCR (Figure 2.4.1c).

Figure 2.4.1c. Sand gazelle distribution 2023.

Predicted distribution calculations are based on a combination of random and circular observations data.

Other target species

Table 2.4.1a shows other target species recorded during the species encounters in quadrant survey. Methods used were circular and random observations.

Table 2.4.1a. Other target species recorded by circular and random observations.

Species	Total recorded	Circular observations	Random encounters
MacQueen's bustard	1	1	0
Arabian hare	2	0	2
Arabian red fox	3	1	2
Pharaoh eagle-owl	5	2	3
Greater hoopoe-lark	9	5	4
Arabian great shrike	28	9	19

Only a single McQueen's bustard was recorded in the central part of the reserve, in front of the pens at Manana farm. These pens are under responsibility of Engineer's Office and contain mustard grass, intended to support the bustards' adaptation after being released into the reserve by the National Avian Research Centre.

Arabian hares were observed mainly in the north of the reserve. Most of their records came from camera traps, as they are an elusive species.

A total of nine greater hoopoe-larks were recorded during the circular and random observations, in all three non-perimeter zones of the reserve.

A total of 28 Arabian great shrikes were recorded during the circular and random observations. They too were observed in all three non-perimeter zones of the reserve, with most sightings near the Manana farm area where an artificial lake is located.

2.4.2. Arabian red fox den surveys

The expedition surveyed a total of 118 dens, of which 26 had previously been classified as active or inactive during the 2020 expedition, and 32 were newly identified dens (10 active and 22 inactive) (Figure 2.4.2a). 17 dens were classified as active, 26 as inactive, and 75 as abandoned. Kernel density analysis revealed the concentration of active and inactive dens to be mostly in the south and central parts of the DDCR, where there is little to no human activity and abundant vegetation (Figure 2.4.2c). Only one active den was recorded in the north of the DDCR. A total of 349 Arabian red fox dens have been recorded and classified in the reserve since 2011 (Figure 2.4.2b).

Figure 2.4.2a. Arabian red fox den survey results of the 2023 expedition.

Table 2.6.2a. Results of the Arabian red fox den surveys in 2011 and 2016-2023. AUCA results are not part of this table. *Previously abandoned dens were not surveyed in 2019 and 2020.

Status	2011	2016	2017	2018	2019*	2020*	2023
Active	66	59	24	11	15	6	17
Inactive	95	52	40	42	29	30	26
Abandoned	0	57	138	167	49	32	75
TOTAL	161	168	202	220	93	68	118
Status changes							
Unchanged		55	65	138	62	6	28
New Active		4	14	7	11	2	10
Inactive to Active		25	2	2	1	2	2
New Inactive		3	24	8	19	21	20
Active to Inactive		24	3	10	2	5	1
Active to Abandoned		12	43	17	6	8	2
Inactive to Abandoned		45	39	25	35	24	17
Not Surveyed		0	11	10	0*	0*	10
Abandoned to Inactive							1
New Inactive							2

Figure 2.4.2b. Results of the Arabian red fox den surveys since 2011.

Figure 2.4.2c. Arabian red fox den distribution in 2020

2.4.3. Camera trapping

One hundred thirty-five camera trapping days captured 4,574 images. 1,700 of these contained recognisable subjects, of which 1,697 were native fauna, and 183 of which were humans or vehicles (Figure 2.4.3a). Two of the nine traps set, camera trap 2 and camera trap 14, malfunctioned and did not record images for one or both weeks. Fifteen wildlife species could be identified from the trapping effort, of which eight were mammal species. The most frequently recorded species was the Arabian gazelle with 1,128 pictures (66%), followed by the Arabian oryx with 227 images (13%), and finally the sand gazelle with 225 images (13%). The remaining species results can be found in Table 2.4.3a.

Figure 2.4.3a. Camera trapping results.

Arabian gazelles were the most abundant with 115 individuals recorded on six traps.

The Arabian oryx was the second most abundant, but first most widespread species, with 65 individuals recorded on seven camera traps.

The third most abundant species was the sand gazelle with 49 individuals from five camera traps.

Other species recorded include the Arabian red fox (four individuals from three camera traps), Arabian hare (four individuals from two camera traps), jerboa (one individual), and a cat (one individual) (Annex #). Whether it was an Arabian wildcat *Felis lybica lybica*, or a feral tabby *Felis catus* is uncertain.

Five bird species were recorded from six camera traps: one Arabian babbler *Turdoides squamiceps*, one desert wheatear *Oenanthe deserti*, three grey francolins *Francolinus pondicerianus*, three black-crowned sparrow-larks *Eremopetrix nigriceps* and 19 Eurasian collared doves *Streptopelia decaocto* (Table 2.4.3b).

Table 2.4.3a. Results of camera trapping 2023, the total number of animals counted in images.

Species	Images recorded	% of images	No. of animals in images
Arabian oryx	227	4.96	65
Arabian gazelle	1128	24.66	115
Sand gazelle	225	4.91	49
Arabian red fox	12	0.26	4
Cat	3	0.06	1
Arabian hare	20	0.43	4
Jerboa	3	0.06	1
Grey francolin	6	0.13	3
Arabian babbler	3	0.06	1
Desert wheatear	2	0.04	1
Black-crowned sparrow-lark	12	0.26	3
Eurasian collared dove	57	1.24	19
Runner ant	27	0.59	7
Giant ant	3	0.06	1
Sand wasp	1	0.02	1
Total	1700		275

Table 2.4.3b Camera trapping results by number of individuals captured.

Trap number	Latitude	Longitude	Arabian oryx	Arabian gazelle	Sand gazelle	Arabian red fox	Cat	Arabian hare	Jerboa	Arabian babbler	Desert wheatear	Grey francolin	Black-crowned sparrow-lark	Eurasian collared dove	Runner ant	Giant ant	Sand wasp
Trap 02	55.655953	24.904303	1	1	4	0	0	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
Trap 03	55.660494	24.869189	7	38	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	3	7	1	1
Trap 04	55.665463	24.900862	4	6	30	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0
Trap 06	55.65594	24.850245	2	10	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Trap 07	55.647524	24.766422	34	7	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Trap 12	55.626555	24.819682	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Trap 13	55.616534	24.779901	5	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Trap 14	55.693987	24.762744	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Trap 17	55.703251	24.820728	12	53	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	10	0	0	0
Total			65	115	49	4	1	4	1	1	1	3	3	19	7	1	1

2.4.4. Pharaoh eagle-owl survey

This expedition recorded a total of ten pharaoh eagle-owls, five from circular and random observations, and five from the dedicated owl survey. Eight of the surveyed sites registered pharaoh eagle-owl activity or presence. Eight possible new nests were found at six sites, one of which was at the Al Fawi farm where base camp was located and the record made outside dedicated survey time (Figure 2.4.4a). Two nesting sites were confirmed, one in the central zone (at a tour operator camp) and one in the south zone of the reserve. Citizen scientists were unable to survey one of the sites as it is the location of a tour operator camp. However, tour operator staff were able to confirm the presence of owls and a nest there. The nest found in the south zone was in the same location recorded during the 2022 breeding season by DDCR staff. This nest was raided and the eggs consumed by a fox during the second week of the expedition. A total of five owls were sighted in four of the survey sites (Table 2.4.4a), in the north and south zones of the reserve.

Figure 2.4.4a. Pharaoh eagle-owl survey areas 2023.

Table 2.4.4a. Pharaoh eagle-owl survey results.

Site	Owls observed	Status 2022	Status 2023
Jebel Nazwa	1	Nesting site	Roosting and possible nesting site
Ruwayyan Farm	0	-	-
Lake Al Idmi	0	-	-
East Ghaf Grove 1	0	-	Nesting site**
East Ghaf Grove 2	1	Nesting site	-
Central 1	0	Nesting site	-
Central 2	0	Nesting site	-
Central 3	0	Nesting site	-
Middle Gate	0	Nesting site	-
West Ghaf Grove	0	Nesting site	Roosting and possible nesting site
Manana Farm	0	-	-
Suhail Farm	0	-	-
South 1	0	-	-
South 2	0	-	Possible nesting site
Perimeter 1	0	-	Roosting site
Perimeter 2	1	-	-
Perimeter 3	0	-	-
Perimeter 4	0	-	-
Perimeter 5	0	-	-
Perimeter 6	0	-	-
Perimeter 7	2	Nesting site	Nesting site
Perimeter 8	0	Roosting site	-
Perimeter 9	0	Roosting site	-
Faqah Waterhole	0	Roosting site	-
New 1	0		Roosting site
New 2	0		Roosting site
New 3	1*		Possible nesting site
New 4	0		Possible nesting site
Total	5		

*Recorded during random observations. **Nesting site at Sand Sherpa camp.

In general, pharaoh eagle-owls were found to be concentrated in the central and south zones of the reserve, in areas with ghaf trees and/or an abundance of large fire bush shrubs (*Leptadenia pyrotechnica*) (Figure 2.4.4b).

Figure 2.4.4b. Pharaoh eagle-owl distribution 2023. Predicted distribution calculations are based on a combination of random, circular, and dedicated survey observations.

2.4.5. Lappet-faced vulture survey

No vultures were observed at any of the survey sites while carrying out the lappet-faced vulture survey.

2.5. Discussion

2.5.1. Species encounter in quadrants

Arabian oryx

Weekly game counts carried out by DDCR staff yielded an average of 300 Arabian oryx inside the reserve during the expedition. During the same period, citizen scientists recorded 512. Although the total amount represents 170% of the known population, if we view the results separately per week and compare them to DDCR's staff counts, we can see that they are a more or less accurate representation of the Arabian oryx population present inside the reserve. The inflated total is almost certainly due to repeat counting of the same individuals over the two-week period. In addition, expedition participants rotated surveys daily, which makes keeping track of roaming herds impossible. Even with these limitations, results show clearly that oryx prefer the south of the reserve, probably because this is where two feeding spots are located and because of the high amount of vegetation in the area. The southern half of the DDCR also has minimal human activity and contains habitats such as gravel plains, sand sheets, and vegetated dunes, which make it more richly vegetated than the north. The year's heavy rainfall also helped produce favourable conditions that provided oryx with ample foraging opportunities in the south.

Arabian gazelle

Weekly game counts carried out by DDCR staff yielded an average of 318 individuals inside the reserve, while citizen scientists counted 299 individuals during the expedition. This difference is within normal error margins for a field project.

Sand gazelle

The weekly game counts carried out by DDCR staff yielded an average of 90 individuals inside the reserve, while citizen scientists counted 265 individuals during the expedition. This overestimation probably stems from the difficulty of telling Arabian from sand gazelle, especially for the untrained citizen science eye. Due to the favourable vegetation conditions in the DDCR during the expedition, sand gazelles were mainly grazing on the natural vegetation among the dunes, which likely played a role in the results as it made spotting them more difficult. Despite this, the expedition helped the DDCR gain a better understanding of sand gazelle distribution.

Figures 2.5.1a & b show the results of the 2023 expedition's ungulate distribution surveys compared to the estimated DDCR population, as determined by the weekly DDCR staff counts.

Figure 2.5.1a. Ungulates recorded by the expedition compared to DDCR weekly counts.

Figure 2.5.1b. Ungulates recorded by the expedition compared to DDCR weekly counts.

Concentrating the species encounter surveys in the quadrants led to minimised double counting in previous expeditions (Moayyed Sher Shah, 2020), but yielded inaccurate data for two of our ungulate species this year (see above). Also, the 2023 expedition consisted of two one-week groups, instead of just one group, as usual. In addition, good rainfall in late 2022 and early 2023 resulted in improved vegetation condition throughout the DDCR. As such, all ungulate species were feeding mainly on natural vegetation. While this creates optimal foraging opportunities for oryx and gazelle, it also makes keeping track of them more difficult as they tend to roam much more. Having said all this, distribution assessment derived from the data is still usable thanks to the use of Inverse Distance Weighted Interpolation. This interpolation method assumes nearby points have greater influence on an unmeasured location than points further away, which makes it a very useful spatial analysis tool for when it is difficult to cover an entire area. Using this allowed us to link the recorded number of individuals of a species to the geographical location of survey points, creating heat maps that show species distribution based on density of individuals across the geographical area of DDCR (ArcGIS, 2023; Geography, 2023).

The single record of McQueen's bustard is likely a function of the species' remarkable camouflage, which makes them very hard to spot despite their large size (70 cm length). National Avian Research Centre (NARC) released great numbers of McQueen's bustards in the DDCR in the past to support wild populations (Roy, 2019). However, we believe that there may be a resident population established inside the reserve as DDCR staff regularly report untagged individuals.

This year the Arabian hare was mainly recorded in the north of the reserve, as opposed to the 2020 expedition where it was mainly recorded in the central and south zones. This could be due to high fox activity and density in the south, forcing hares to move and become even more elusive to avoid predation.

2.5.2. Arabian red fox den surveys

The well-vegetated sites recorded the highest den densities for both active and inactive dens. These sites were dominated by tall shrubs, particularly *Leptadenia pyrotechnica*, which meet the habitat requirements of providing a stable soil substrate supported by the shrub's root system (Sher Shah, M. et al., 2020). The 2023 red fox den surveys also revealed an increase in the number of surveyed or identified active and inactive dens compared to 2020. However, 73% of the dens previously classified as active and inactive in 2020 were found abandoned by the 2023 expedition. This could have been caused by the heavy rainfall experienced during late 2022 and early 2023, which likely caused dens to collapse (Moayyed Sher Shah, 2020). Furthermore, red foxes are known to have several dens they can use as part of their survival strategy. Therefore, a large number of abandoned dens does not necessarily reflect a decrease in population (Amadeus J. D. DeKastle, 2022). Comparing the results of the Arabian red fox den survey over the years shows that while most dens were probably discovered between 2016 and 2018, the number of active fox dens has been, in general, increasing over the last five years (Figure 2.4.2b).

The red fox itself was recorded on three camera traps during the expedition and there were several sightings recorded by DDCR staff after the end of the expedition, between February and May 2023. Good vegetation conditions observed after the winter rains will likely have a favourable impact on fox prey base, further adding positive indicators for the Arabian red fox population in the DDCR. Despite this, however, we note that finding and classifying fox dens is a difficult task for citizen scientists, which will invariably affect results (Moayyed Sher Shah, 2020). In order to gather more reliable data, the amount of time and the training method employed for this survey should be revised.

2.5.3. Camera trapping

During the 2020 expedition, the camera trapping effort was close to half compared to 2023 (80 trapping days), yet yielded significantly more pictures (6,609 in 2020 vs 4,574 in 2023). This is largely due to camera traps malfunctioning and a reduction in the amount of camera traps employed (nine as opposed to 16 in 2020). However, the number of species recorded was very similar with 12 for 2020 and 15 for 2023. This suggests that the amount of time the camera traps stay in the field may be more relevant than the number of cameras used.

The 2023 camera trap survey recorded three of the six target species of this expedition, namely the Arabian oryx, Arabian gazelle and sand gazelle. Three of the remaining target species (lappet-faced vulture, pharaoh eagle-owl and MacQueen's bustard) were observed during other surveys. These results are not surprising as we know, from permanent monitoring programmes, that both raptor species prefer areas with waterholes and the McQueen's bustard is a rare record most years (unpublished monitoring results).

Among the target mammal species, the Arabian red fox was recorded by three camera traps, two in the north and one in the central zone. This seems to contrast with results from the den survey, which indicates the highest fox density lies in the south zone, but since camera trapping is a very focused point count prone to large variations, this is no cause for concern. Cameras 3 and 4 were placed at irrigated sites where vegetation is enhanced, creating favourable conditions for desert rodents which are an important food item in fox diets. Camera 17 was placed in a gravel plain where spiny-tailed lizard *Uromastix aegyptia leptieni* activity has been recorded. These reptiles have also been recorded as a food item in fox diet. In contrast, most of the other camera traps were placed in sand dune habitats, where finding prey may be more difficult due to more scattered vegetation.

The Arabian hare was a rare record obtained from two camera traps placed in sand dune habitat in the north zone. These sites benefit the hare as it relies on its camouflaged fur for protection, blending with the surrounding sand when sitting still (personal observations).

Although the presence of the Arabian wildcat could not be confirmed from this expedition's results, the species was recorded sometime later through one of the reserve's permanent monitoring programmes.

2.5.4. Pharaoh eagle-owl survey

In previous years, records of Pharaoh eagle-owl during expeditions relied exclusively on random and circular observations, resulting in a low number of sightings. Implementing a dedicated survey for this species resulted in record observations over the past six years (Figure 2.5.4a). A dedicated pharaoh eagle-owl survey also helped us explore possible nesting grounds that had been difficult to check thoroughly with the available staff, such as Jebel Nazwa. Citizen scientists hiked through these areas to check for owl activity in the numerous holes and crevices present (Figure 2.8.3b), discovering abundant traces of owl activity throughout. This included a pharaoh eagle-owl roosting near the waterhole every day for the duration of the expedition.

Reutilisation of previous nesting sites by a breeding pair was also recorded during the expedition. During the 2022 breeding season DDCR Conservation staff Basil Roy and Dean D'Silva recorded and georeferenced a pharaoh eagle-owl nest in the reserve's south perimeter, under a large *Leptadenia* bush. This year, during the first week of the expedition, when citizen scientists revisited the site, they saw a large eagle-owl flying out from under the bush and found that it again contained a nest. We suspect this nest belongs to the same pair of owls that was recorded nesting at the site in 2022.

Little is known about the pharaoh eagle-owl breeding ecology, and nesting dynamics have not yet been studied, making this one of only a few published records of the species reusing a nesting site (Moldovan & Sandor, 2009). Nest site fidelity has been recorded in other eagle-owl species and seems to play a part in their reproductive success (Pande, et al., 2011; Frank & Lutz, 1997; Dalbeck & Heg, 2006). Although this nest was later preyed upon by a fox, the site should continue to be monitored in future years to assess if this will deter owls from using the site again. There are studies done on other raptor species that link nest fidelity to higher predation risks, a factor which has not yet been studied in this species (Otterbeck, Selås, Nielsen, Roualet, & Lindén, 2019; Pande, et al., 2011). Continuous monitoring of pharaoh eagle-owl in the DDCR will provide us with valuable data on their reproductive ecology, nesting dynamics and population status, allowing for decision making and management practices that will aid in the conservation of this species.

Figure 2.5.4a. Pharaoh eagle-owl observations 2017-2023.

2.5.5. Lappet-faced vulture survey

Vultures were not observed at any of the survey sites during the dedicated survey. This could have been due to a combination of unfavourable weather conditions, such as very high winds and heavy rains. This may have also been a result of plain bad luck, as camera trap data later showed that the selected sites were indeed visited by vultures during the expedition, but citizen scientists just missed them. Despite zero results from this survey, we were able to do a distribution assessment using circular and random observations, with most vultures spotted in the central and southern zones (Figure 2.5.5b).

After the biggest sighting of vultures in 2016, the number of vulture sightings made a steep drop, but has remained relatively constant over the past four years (Figure 2.5.5a). This suggests that, while there is no evidence of vultures breeding yet, the DDCR remains an important part of their home range. The reserve provides a safe and steady amount of food as, in general, animal carcasses are left where they fall to allow for natural nutrient recycling cycles to take place. In the events where tour operators report dead animals at their camp sites, these are moved to a dedicated location, Carcass Point, where they can be accessed by vultures, and other scavengers, and used to study their feeding ecology (Figure 2.3.5b). The DDCR also provides constant water sources through the seven artificial ponds and two artificial lakes within the reserve.

Given the results, it is unlikely that this survey will be included again in future expeditions. However, vulture monitoring will continue to take place through camera trap surveys and random observations by DDCR staff.

Figure 2.5.5a. Lappet-faced vulture observations 2016-2023.

Figure 2.5.5b. Lappet-faced vulture distribution 2023.
 Predicted distribution calculations are based on a combination of random and circular observations.

2.6. Conclusions and management considerations

Ungulate counts performed by the expedition are useful as they help us confirm numbers determined by the DDCR staff during weekly game counts. They also serve to determine whether citizen scientists are able to differentiate between gazelle species. However, if there are multi-group expeditions in future, modifications to both methodology and logistics will be required to ensure data quality.

Continuous monitoring of other target species, such as McQueen's bustard and the Arabian hare, is necessary to evaluate their population inside the DDCR and understand their role in the ecosystem.

Additionally, since their construction in 2021, the enclosures outside the DDCR have been home to an increasing number of surplus Arabian oryx that have been extracted from the reserve to reduce overgrazing and maintain a balanced ecosystem. Translocation of these oryx to other reserves within their natural home range has been approved and there is a high probability that all individuals inside the enclosures will be translocated by the end of 2023. This will enable us to resume extraction of surplus individuals from the reserve and the removal of feeding spots altogether. Reducing the ungulate population in the DDCR will lead to healthier vegetation conditions and species distribution dependent on habitat type and quality, rather than supplementary feed. Predator re-introduction has not yet been approved by the authorities, but is still under consideration as it would encourage natural population dynamics (Moayyed Sher Shah, 2020).

Although the Arabian red fox den survey this year returned more active dens than the previous expedition, overall den surveys have shown a declining trend. Nonetheless, other indications, from camera traps and sightings, suggest a steadily rising population. The number of active dens surveyed does warrant further investigation over a larger area to gain a better understanding of the Arabian red fox population in the DDCR. However, bearing in mind the difficulty in differentiating active and inactive dens there is a need to increase (or otherwise modify) training given to citizen scientists. Considering that the survey focuses only on revisiting known dens, an intensive survey, covering all 62 quadrants, is necessary to gain a clearer picture of Arabian red fox populations inside the DDCR. This could be included as part of the next expedition.

Camera trap surveys have been part of the DDCR's conservation actions for over 15 years. Continuous camera trap surveys therefore remain an important aspect of monitoring target species in the DDCR.

Pharaoh eagle-owl records increased almost two-fold compared to previous years due to the dedicated survey conducted to evaluate population status and nesting behaviour of this species. Several new activity sites were identified, with three new roosting sites and three new possible nesting sites recorded. A novel record of nest reutilisation for this species was also possible thanks to this expedition's results. Based on the above, a dedicated pharaoh eagle-owl survey is necessary and should continue to be included in future expeditions to gain a better understanding of the species' distribution, population status and breeding ecology within the DDCR.

Given the results, lappet-faced vulture surveys will not be included in future expeditions. However, vulture monitoring will continue to take place in the reserve through camera trap surveys and random observations by DDCR staff.

Recommendations for the 2024 expedition

We recommend the 2024 expedition continue with the survey activities described in this report, apart from the lappet-faced vulture survey. Emphasis should be put into improving the following:

- During each circular and random observation, the group structure and composition of ungulates should be recorded for each group observed.
- More efforts should be made by participants to observe and identify bird species, particularly the greater hoopoe-lark, during the circular and random observations in DDCR.
- The red fox den survey should be expanded in training and effort to differentiate between active/inactive dens and discover new dens. Intensive systematic surveys for dens should be carried out, covering all 62 quadrants in the reserve to elucidate population status.
- Camera trapping should be continued with the locations selected for the 2023 expedition, with all nine camera traps placed on natural sites. However, camera traps should be tested in the field prior to the expedition to make sure they work properly.
- The pharaoh eagle-owl survey should be continued, and more emphasis should be placed on completely surveying Jebel Nazwa. Training should also be expanded to help differentiate owl nests from those of other birds.

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